

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Anorue, D.N. Haemato-Biochemical Indices and Immune Response of Grower Pigs Fed Enzyme Supplemented Dried Cassava Peel –Maize Cob Composite Meal. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2024; Vol 3, Issue 1, pp. 106-113.

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

***Corresponding Author**

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

Email: anorued@gmail.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 2nd April, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 23/April / 2024 to 23rd May/2024

Accepted: 24th May 2024

Published: May 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integatemind-journal>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

License: **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

Haemato-Biochemical Indices and Immune Response of Grower Pigs Fed Enzyme Supplemented Dried Cassava Peel –Maize Cob Composite Meal

Daniel Nnadozie Anorue ^{1*}

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to examine the haemato-biochemical and immune response of grower pigs fed enzyme supplemented dried Cassava peel-maize cob composite meal (CPM-CM). A total of 36 crossbreed male grower pigs (Large white) of about 16 weeks' old were randomly distributed into four groups of nine animals per treatment. Each treatment was further divided into three replicates consisting of three pigs in a completely randomized design. Pigs in treatment 1 were fed 0 % CPM-CM while CPM-CM was used to replace maize at 40 % (T2), 50 % (T3) and 60 % in T4. Examination of phyto-constituents in CPM-CM showed that it contains alkaloids, tannins, saponins, cyanide, phenols and flavonoids at 20.05 mg/kg, 9.06 mg/kg, 10.04 mg/kg, 15.03 mg/kg, 8.92 mg/kg and 14.11 mg/kg respectively. Haematological results revealed that red blood cell, pack cell volume, haemoglobin, mean corpuscular haemoglobin, mean corpuscular volume, mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration, white blood cell, monocytes and lymphocytes were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the treatment except for basophils count ($P > 0.05$). Total protein, total bilirubin, glucose, creatinine, alkaline phosphatase, alanine transaminase and aspartate transaminase values were significantly different among the treatment ($P < 0.05$) except for cholesterol and urea levels. It was concluded that all the blood parameters evaluated were within the established range for healthy pigs and dietary replacement of CPM-CM with maize up to 60 % pose no deleterious effect on the health of the animals.

Keywords: Cassava peel; Enzyme; Nutrition; Haematology; Pigs; Serum.

1. INTRODUCTION

Worldwide population growth, rising incomes and urbanization are triggering an explosion in the demand for high quality protein. By 2030, the World Health Organization (WHO) projects annual meat production to reach 376 million tons globally up from 218 million tons in 1997-1999 (Dan, 2021). One of the major constraints of the development of livestock industry in developing countries including Nigeria is the high cost of conventional feedstuffs (Odunsi et al., 2013) due to stiff competition between human and animals. Maize constitutes about 60 % of feed which also serves as food for many households in Nigeria. Competition between man and livestock for maize, soya beans among others is often responsible for high cost of these ingredients (Oladunjoye et al., 2005). Several studies have been carried out on many energy supplying agricultural products as substitute for maize in swine feed. Among such products that have been tried are sweet potatoes, cocoyam, yam, rice by-products, peels of tubers, molasses, sorghum and wheat (Oladunjoye et al., 2017). One of such agro-industrial by-product is cassava peels and maize cob which are cheaper unconventional alternative feed resources for livestock animals (Anuore et al., 2024). Cassava peel has to be processed to reduce the toxicity caused by some of its content and this content includes hydrocyanic acid (HCN) which is harmful to animals. Cassava is processed by various methods to increase acceptability and palatability by animals. Several processing methods have been applied over the years. Cassava peel can be processed using any of the following methods: grating and sun-drying, boiling, parboiling and sun-drying (Salami and Odunsi, 2003).

SHERWAN
Publishers

Studies have also revealed that cassava peel and maize cob mixture can be used to replace maize up to 30 % in the diet of weaner pigs without causing any negative effect on their performance (Anuore et al., 2024). Ojediran et al. (2019), also reported a non-significant difference in blood parameters of growing pigs fed cassava peel at 50 % replacement. There is a direct relationship between nutrition and blood parameters (Shittu et al., 2021). However, there is scanty information on the use of cassava peel/maize cob meal mixture in grower pigs. A timely, evaluation will give a clue on the optimum replacement level and also help to use cassava peel/maize cob meal mixture to bridge the gap between livestock production and sustainability. Therefore, this research was designed to examine the haemato-biochemical indices and immune response of grower pigs fed enzyme supplemented dried cassava peel –maize cob composite meal.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental site

This study was conducted at the University of Abuja Teaching and Research Farm, Main Campus, along Airport Road, Gwagwalada, Abuja, Nigeria; the Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Gwagwalada, situated between latitudes 8°57'1" and 8°55'1"N and longitudes 7°05'1" and 7°06'1"E, serves as the headquarters of the Gwagwalada Area Council (NPC, 2006).

2.2. Obtaining and getting ready test materials

Fresh maize cobs and cassava peels were gathered from several Gwagwalada Cassava/maize processing facilities. For a duration of 16 days, the samples were exposed to sunlight in order to lower their anti-nutritional factor levels and prevent microbial responses that could cause spoiling and nutrient leaching. After being individually ground into meals in a hammer mill and treated with a multi-enzyme before it was mixed with other ingredients. Samples of each meal was taken into the laboratory for additional examination.

2.3. Experimental animals, design and management

Thirty-six male large white grower pigs, aged 16 weeks, were purchased from a well-known farm in Abuja. The animals were kept in quarantine for a period of two weeks, fed a basal diet designed to satisfy the needs of grower pigs in accordance with the NRC's (2002) recommendation, and given preventive treatment, which included injections of long-acting Oxytetracycline at a rate of 2 mL/20 kg body weight and subcutaneous Ivermectin® at a rate of 0.5 mL/25 kg of body weight to control ecto and endo parasites. Pigs were divided into four treatment groups according to body weight, and each treatment was fully randomized and repeated three times with three animals in each replicate. Feeding was place twice a day at 8:00 and 16:00, and everyday access to fresh, clean water was provided. Daily feed intake was calculated by subtracting the left over from the feed supplied while the weight was taken weekly. All other management procedures were rigorously followed during the three-month duration of the investigation.

2.4. Experimental diets

Four experimental diets were formulated to meet the nutrient requirements for swine according to NRC (2002). Cassava peel and maize cob meal (CPM-CM) at ratio 1:1 was incorporated into the experimental diet to replace maize as follows: treatment 1 (T1) control diet (0 % CPM-CM), T2 (40 % CPM-CM), T3 (50 % CPM-CM), T4 (60 % CPM-CM) as presented in Table 1.

2.5. Data collected

2.5.1. Blood collection and analysis

Two pigs per replicate making a total of six pigs per treatment were chosen on the 12th day of the experiment for hemo-biochemical measurement. During the blood collection process, a stress-free environment was maintained for a selected group of animals to avoid deoxygenating the oxygenated blood. The pigs under study had their jugular veins bled in order to extract 4 millilitres of blood per animal. Of this volume, 2 millilitres were placed in a bijoux bottle and subjected to ethylene diamine tetra acetate treatment for haematological testing, while the remaining 2 millilitres were utilised for serum analysis. The Sysmex XN-3100 automated analyzer equipment was utilised to perform haematological analysis on red blood cells, haemoglobin, packed cell volume, white blood cells, and their respective differentials.

Two millilitres of blood were drawn and placed into bottles free of ethylene, diamine, tetraacetic acid, and then subjected to tests for serum biochemical indices, including total protein, creatinine, uric acid, bilirubin, lipoproteins, cholesterol, glucose, calcium, phosphorus, potassium, sodium, bicarbonate, and enzymes. The Analytica 705 clinical diagnostics system was used for the analysis. The technical specifications included optical flow (30 µL quartz), reaction volume (350–1000 µL), photometric range (-0.1 to 3.0 absorbance), and filter (7 interference filters: 340, 405, 505, 546, 578, 620, and 670 nm).

2.5.2. Immunological status estimation

The blood specimens utilized for haematological examination were used to perform immune-globulin (A, G, and M) activities. The MAGICL 6000 chemilum immunoassay analyzer, made in China, was used for the analysis. Samples were organised in the sample chamber and the temperature was adjusted to 32 ° C. The monitor (output unit) showed the findings of each parameter. Technical

information included in the commercial kit includes the following information: technique (fluorescence enzyme immunoassay); detection (LED illuminant, non-flow cell); reaction time (antigen antibody reaction: 10 minutes); highest sample load limit (25 samples); sample container (primary tube, 13 × 75/100 mm, 16 × 75/100 mm diameter); temperature (15 – 30 ° C); and humidity (40 – 80 percent).

2.5.3. Phytochemical analysis in test ingredients

Concentrations of phytochemicals in maize cob and cassava peel were determined using standard procedures outlined by Sofowora (2009).

2.6. Statistical analysis

Data collected from the study was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the computer software package SPSS 22.0; differences among treatment means were compared with Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1995).

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The phytochemical composition of cassava peel meal showed that it contains alkaloids (8.06 mg/kg), tannins (4.51 mg/kg), saponins (2.72 mg/g), cyanide (16.03 mg/g), flavonoids (7.66 mg/g) and phenols (3.91 mg/kg) (see, Table 1). Maize cob meal has a higher proportion of alkaloids (10.88 mg/g), followed by saponins (6.87 mg/g), flavonoids (5.00 mg/g), tannins (3.91 mg/g) and phenol (2.92 mg/g). Cassava peel/maize cob meal mixture (CPM-CM) treated with enzymes revealed showed that alkaloids (20.05 mg/g), tannins (9.06 mg/g), saponins (10.04 mg/g), cyanide (15.03 mg/g), flavonoids (14.11 mg/g) and phenols (8.92 mg/g). The cyanide content (15.03 mg/g) recorded in this study is within the tolerable range (50.00 mg/kg) for monogastric animal reported by Okoli et al. (2012).

Table 1: Gross composition of the experimental diets (% DM)

Ingredients	T1 (0 %)	T2 (40 %)	T3 (50 %)	T4 (60 %)
Maize	60.00	36.00	30.00	24.00
Wheat offal	8.00	8.00	8.00	8.00
Soya beans	17.30	17.30	17.30	17.30
Groundnut cake	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.50
CPM-CM	0.00	24.00	30.00	36.00
Bone meal	3.03	3.03	3.03	3.03
Limestone	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50
Methionine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Lysine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
*Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Salt	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Determined analysis				
Crude protein (%)	15.10	14.34	14.22	14.20
Crude fibre (%)	6.00	8.12	8.87	9.01
Ether extract (%)	2.40	2.37	2.35	2.30
Calcium (%)	1.83	1.83	1.83	1.83
Phosphorus (%)	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67
Energy (Kcal/kg)	2801.8	2798.5	2779.6	2765.9

Note: *Vitamin A, 8,000 I.U., Vitamin E, 5 mg, Vitamin D3, 3000 I.U., Vitamin K, 3 mg, Vitamin B2, 5.5 mg, Niacin, 25 mg, Vitamin B12, 16 mg, Choline chloride, 120 mg, Mn, 5.2 mg, Zn, 25 mg, Cu, 2.6 mg, Folic acid, 2 mg, Fe, 5 mg, Pantothenic acid, 10 mg, Biotin, 30.5 mg, and antioxidant, 56 mg are provided as a premix per kilogram meal.

Table 2 shows that alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins and phenols have different therapeutic properties such as, analgesics, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, hepato-protective, immune-stimulatory activities amongst others (Daniel

Table 2: Phytochemical composition of maize cob and cassava peel meal

Specifications (mg/kg)	Cassava peel meal	Maize cob meal	**CPM-CM
Alkaloids	9.00	10.88	20.05
Tannins	4.51	3.91	9.06
Saponins	2.72	6.87	10.04
Cyanide	15.03	-	15.03
Flavonoids	7.66	5.00	14.11
Phenols	3.91	2.92	8.92

Note: **CPM-CM: Cassava peel/maize cob meal mixture treated with enzymes

Haematological parameters of grower pigs fed cassava peel – maize cob meal mixture as replacement for maize (Table 3). The dietary treatment influenced ($P<0.05$) the pack cell volume (PCV), haemoglobin (Hb), platelets, red blood cell (RBC), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentrations (MCHC), white blood cell (WBC), neutrophils, monocytes and leucocytes values except for basophil count ($P>0.05$). Pack cell volume, Hb, platelet, MCV, MCH, MCHC, WBC, neutrophils, monocytes and leucocyte count were higher ($P<0.05$) in T3 and T4 relative to the other groups. Hematological analysis is routinely used in veterinary medicine to evaluate the health status of animals and poultry (Mafuvadze and Erlwanger, 2007). Haematological values could serve as base line information for comparison in condition of nutrient deficiency, physiology and health status of farm animals (Daramola *et al.*, 2005). The results obtained in this study shows that the dietary treatment had significant ($P<0.05$) effect on all the observed hematological parameters of growing pigs. Togunet *et al.* (2007) state that when an animal's haematological values are within the normal range that has been defined for it, there was no negative effect of the diet during the trial period. In terms of trend, the PCV was greater in T4, closely followed by T3, T2, and T1 (control). The results are consistent with those of Adesehinwa *et al.* (2011), who observed that in growing pigs fed diets based on cassava peel meal (CPM) and CPM + Farmazyme-3000, the enzyme marginally increased PCV but not above that of a diet based on maize. Increased cells destruction and subsequent enhanced erythropoiesis in the liver, spleen, and kidneys cause macrocytic (regenerative) anaemia, which is indicated by reductions in concentrations of erythrocyte parameters (e.g., packed cell volume (PCV), red blood cell counts (RBC), and haemoglobin (Hb) concentration) and elevations in MCV (Jain, 1986). The study's haemoglobin readings fell between the ideal ranges for developing pigs (Merck's Veterinary Manual, 2010). According to Merck's Veterinary Manual (2010), this further implies that the anti-nutritional components in cassava peel had been reduced to a manageable, non-fatal level, which explains why all the haematological measures were within normal limits. This corroborates the findings of Maxwell *et al.* (2000a) who asserted that ingestion of dietary components had measurable effect on blood composition and may be considered as appropriate measure of long term nutritional status (Olabanjiet *et al.*, 2007). Thus, everything that has an impact on blood, like diet, will undoubtedly have a negative or moderate effect on the body's overall health, growth, maintenance, and reproduction (Okeet *et al.*, 2007). According to Etime *et al.* (2014), there was a correlation between the nutritional state of animals and haematological features, specifically PCV and Hb. Even in cases when an animal did not exhibit overt clinical symptoms of illness, PCV and other haematological measures might be helpful prognostic tools and may indicate an unfavorable condition (Ezeet *et al.*, 2010). The fact that the concentration values of haematological features in this study did not fall below normal suggested that the minor amounts of anti-nutritional elements did not have a detrimental effect on these haematological parameters. The RBC concentration recorded in this study was similar to that of Enyenihi *et al.* (2008). The trend in the RBC, PCV and Hb in this study could be ascribed to the direct relationship among RBC, PCV and Hb (Jain, 1986). According to Kaneko (1989); Musa *et al.* (2021), the normal WBC and their differentials indicated sufficient defense against infectious pathogens. This is most likely because the diets contain enough protein. Daniel and Alagbe (2023); Adewale *et al.* (2021), observed that nutritional shortage, particularly that of protein, reduced most haematological and serum parameters. Based on the comparable results obtained, it is sufficient to declare that the nutrient profiles of the diets were adequate to support the performance of the pigs.

Table 3: Haematological parameters of grower pigs Fed CPM-CM

Specifications	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM	Reference range
Pack cell volume (%)	29.70 ^b	34.11 ^a	35.10 ^a	35.87 ^a	0.02	29.00 – 40.00
Haemoglobin (g/L)	99.56 ^c	107.2 ^b	112.8 ^a	115.9 ^a	1.16	50.00 – 167.1
Platelet ($\times 10^9/L$)	126.90 ^b	139.55 ^a	140.16 ^a	141.80 ^a	1.95	33.4 – 181.0
Mean platelet volume (fl)	6.00 ^b	8.40 ^a	8.55 ^a	8.90 ^a	0.02	1.22 – 11.40
Red blood cell ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	7.05 ^b	9.66 ^a	9.80 ^a	9.94 ^a	0.02	6.40 – 12.30
Mean corpuscular volume (fl)	52.91 ^c	59.00 ^b	65.77 ^a	68.50 ^a	1.00	23.0 – 48.0
MCH (pg)	29.83 ^c	30.40 ^b	34.00 ^a	35.72 ^a	0.02	17.0 – 23.0
MCHC (g/L)	49.02 ^b	56.91 ^a	57.00 ^a	58.15 ^a	0.04	22.0 – 76.9
White blood cell ($\times 10^9/L$)	12.02 ^b	15.00 ^a	15.10 ^a	15.72 ^a	0.01	8.70 – 37.9
Neutrophils ($\times 10^9/L$)	8.78 ^b	10.00 ^a	10.15 ^a	10.85 ^a	0.02	0.09 – 9.71
Basophils ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.13	0.01	0.0 – 0.71
Monocytes ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.96 ^b	1.05 ^b	1.75 ^a	1.89 ^a	0.01	0 – 4.90
Lymphocytes ($\times 10^9/L$)	9.95 ^b	12.00 ^a	12.70 ^a	13.56 ^a	0.01	3.60 – 18.50

Note: ^{a,b,c}Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$); T1: 0 % CPM-CM; T2: 40 % CPM-CM; T3: 50 % CPM-CM; T4: 60 % CPM-CM; SEM: standard error of mean; Reference range : Merck's veterinary manual (2010).

Serum biochemical parameters of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob mixture as replacement for maize is presented in Table 4. Total protein, albumin, globulin, cholesterol, urea, creatinine, total bilirubin, direct bilirubin, glucose, alanine transaminase, aspartate transferase, alanine phosphatase values varied from 6.12 - 7.25 (g/dL), 4.01 - 4.70 g/dL, 2.11 - 2.55 g/dL, 3.00 - 3.11 mmol/L, 2.00 - 2.85 mmol/L, 59.81 - 67.18 mmol/L, 3.70 - 6.28 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, 1.93 - 3.06 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, 73.67 - 74.08 IU/L, 64.84 - 65.67 IU/L and 113.1 - 114.0 (IU/L) respectively. Dietary treatment influenced all parameters except alanine transaminase, aspartate transferase, alanine phosphatase and cholesterol values ($P > 0.05$). The serum total protein and albumin of the growing pigs used in this study were affected ($P < 0.05$) by the treatments. This indicated that the protein level in CPM-CM was able to support the protein reserves of the pigs across the groups. The presence of variations in the serum metabolites could also be attributed to the protein and feed intakes across the groups. According to Gouache *et al.* (1991); Alagbe (2017), a protein deficit has a particular impact on albumin content. The levels found in this investigation fell within the Adesehinwa (2007) normal range. The food therapy had no discernible effect on serum urea, an animal marker of muscle waste (Mitraka and Rawnsley, 1977). Rather, despite the diets' high fibre content, they appeared to have been used well, leading to substantial tissue deposition. The results for creatinine, bilirubin, and cholesterol were all within the recommended ranges for pigs (Alagbe, 2024), indicating that there was no risk of renal failure or excessive fat content in the carcass of the animal. Elevated serum glucose level can be triggered during the period of stress or poor management (Shittuet *et al.*, 2023). ALT, AST and ALP values were within the normal range for healthy pigs (Merck Veterinary Manual, 2010), indicating the absence of liver or health issues (Olafadehan *et al.*, 2023; Alagbe, 2024).

Table 4: Serum Biochemical Parameters of grower pigs fed Cassava peel meal-maize cob mixture (CPM-CM)

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM	Reference range
Total protein (G/DL)	6.12 ^b	7.18 ^a	7.22 ^a	7.25 ^a	0.02	4.40 - 9.21
Albumin (g/dL)	4.01 ^b	4.70 ^a	4.81 ^a	4.70 ^a	0.10	1.90 – 4.00
Globulin (g/dL)	2.11 ^b	2.48 ^a	2.41 ^a	2.55 ^a	0.45	2.00 – 4.20
Cholesterol (MMOL/L)	3.02	3.11	3.09	3.00	0.36	2.00 – 4.50
Urea (MMOL/L)	2.85	2.30	2.00	2.70	0.10	2.90 – 9.93
Creatinine ($\mu\text{MOL/L}$)	59.81 ^c	60.80 ^b	67.00 ^a	67.18 ^a	2.09	67.0 – 188.0
Total bilirubin ($\mu\text{MOL/L}$)	3.70 ^c	5.31 ^b	6.11 ^a	6.28 ^a	0.72	2.00 – 9.50

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM	Reference range
Direct bilirubin ($\mu\text{MOL/L}$)	1.93 ^b	3.03 ^a	3.00 ^a	3.06 ^a	0.12	0 – 4.00
Glucose (MMOL/L)	3.11 ^b	5.66 ^a	5.87 ^a	5.92 ^a	0.25	3.50 – 10.40
ALT (IU/L)	74.08	73.67	74.06	74.07	2.33	15.0 – 98.0
AST (U/L)	65.67	65.00	64.84	65.53	1.97	22.0 – 100.7
ALP (U/L)	113.1	113.5	113.8	114.0	3.55	10.2 – 200.6

Note: ^{a,b,c}Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P<0.05$); T1: 0 % CPM-CM; T2: 40 % CPM-CM; T3: 50 % CPM-CM; T4: 60 % CPM-CM; SEM: standard error of mean; ALT – alanine transaminase, AST- aspartate transferase, ALP- alanine phosphatase; Reference range: Merck's veterinary manual (2010)

The results revealed that there was significant difference ($P<0.05$) in all parameters among all dietary treatments. Pigs fed T3 (50 % CPM-CM) and T4 (60 % CPM-CM) recorded the highest ($P<0.05$) value of IgA, IgG and IgM followed by T2 (40 % CPM-CM) and T1 (0 % CPM-CM). This suggests that the presence of phytochemicals in CPMCM especially flavonoids may pose improve immune functions in pigs. According to Hashem *et al.* (2013); Alagbe (2024), flavonoids has been found to have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and immunomodulation activities. Activities of these phytochemicals in CPM-CM will further maintain a healthy gut in pigs. The result recorded in this study, is in agreement with the findings of Tripathiet *al.* (2008) who used Farmazyme^R supplementation on processed cassava meal to feed growing pigs (see, Table 5).

Table 5: Immune status of grower pigs fed CP-MCM

Specifications	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
IgA ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.58 ^b	2.26 ^{ab}	2.31 ^{ab}	2.97 ^a	0.92
IgG ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	2.70 ^c	2.78 ^c	3.00 ^b	5.93 ^a	0.28
IgM ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.93 ^b	1.98 ^b	2.50 ^a	2.60 ^a	0.85

Note: ^{a,b,c}Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P<0.05$); T1: 0 % CPM-CM; T2: 40 % CPM-CM; T3: 50 % CPM-CM; T4: 60 % CPM-CM; SEM: standard error of mean; IgA:immunoglobulin A; IgG: Immunoglobulin G; IgM: Immunoglobulin M.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that CPM-CM contains several essential nutrients which can positively influence the performance of pigs. Replacing maize with CPM-CM had no deleterious effect on the health status of animals.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Adeshinwa, A.O.K., Obi, O.O., Makanjuola, B.A., Oluwole, O.O., & Adesina, M.A. (2011). Growing pigs fed cassava peel-based diet supplemented with or without Farmazyme® 3000 proenx: Effect on growth, carcass and blood parameters. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 10, 2791-2796.
2. Adewale, A.O., Alagbe, J.O., & Adeoye, A.O. (2021). Dietary supplementation of Rauwolfia vomitoria root extract as a phytogetic feed additive in growing rabbit diets: Haematology and serum biochemical indices. *International Journal of Orange Technologies*, 3(3), 1-12.
3. Alagbe, J.O. (2017a). Growth performance and blood parameters of weaner pigs fed diets supplemented with turmeric powder. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 7(2), 57-61.
4. Alagbe, J.O. (2017b). Nutrient evaluation of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) fruit peel as a replacement for maize in the diets of weaner grass cutters. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 6(8), 277-282.
5. Alagbe, J.O. (2023a). Investigating the effects of dietary supplementation of Eucalyptus camaldulensis essential oil on haemato-biochemical indices, immune response and oxidative stress of weaned rabbits. *International Journal of Agriculture and Animal Production*, 4(1), 34-46.
6. Alagbe, J.O. (2023b). Investigating the effects of dietary supplementation of Eucalyptus camaldulensis essential oil on the growth performance, nutrient digestibility and caecal fermentation of weaned rabbits. *Research in Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences*, 7(3), 139-148.
7. Alagbe, O.J., Anuore, D.N., Shittu, M.D., & Ramalan, S.M. (2023). Growth performance and physiological response of weaned pigs fed diet supplemented with novel phytochemicals. *Brazilian Journal of Science*, 3(1), 43-57.
8. Alagbe, O.J., & Anuore, D.N. (2023). Effect of Doum palm mesocarp meal (*Hyphaene thebaica*) as partial replacement for maize on growth performance and haematological indices of weaned pigs. *Journal of Biotechnology and Bioinformatics Research*, 5(3), 1-6. doi.org/10.47363/JBBR/2023(5)161
9. Alagbe, O.J., Daniel, N.A., Shittu, M.D., Emiola, A., Akande, T., & Adegoke, A.E. (2023). Impact of dietary supplementation of Carica papaya essential oil on the blood chemistry of broiler chickens. *Science Letters*, 11(3), 105-110.
10. Daramola, J.O., Adeloye, A.A., Fatoba, T.A., & Soladoye, A.O. (2005). Haematological and serum biochemical parameters of West African Dwarf goats. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 17(8). Available at: <http://www.irrd.org/17/8/clara/17095.htm>
11. Daniel, N.A., Friday, U., & Alagbe, O.J. (2023). Investigating the effects of pawpaw (*Carica papaya*) essential oil dietary supplementation on the growth performance and carcass characteristics of broilers. *Research in Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences*, 7(3), 164-174.
12. Etim, N.N., Enyenihi, G.E., Akpabio, U., & Offiong, E.E.A. (2014). Effects of nutrition on haematology of rabbits: A review. *European Scientific Journal*, 10(3), 413-424.
13. Jain, N.C. (1986). *Schalm's Veterinary Haematology* (4th ed.). Lea and Febiger.
14. Mathivanan, R., Selvaraj, P., & Nanjappan, K. (2006). Feeding of fermented soybean meal on broiler performance. *International Journal of Poultry Science*, 5, 868-872.
15. Maxwell, M.H., Robertson, G.W., Spence, S., & McCongroudala, C.C. (1990). Composition of haematological values in restricted and ad libitum fed domesticated fowls. *British Poultry Science*, 60, 1474-1484.
16. Merck Veterinary Manual. (2010). Merck Veterinary Manual (10th ed.). Merck and Co. Inc.
17. Mitruka, B.M., & Rawnsley, H. (1977). *Chemical, Biochemical, and Haematological Reference in Normal Experimental Animals*. Mason.
18. Musa, B., Alagbe, J.O., Adegbite, M.B., & Omokore, E.A. (2020). Growth performance, caeca microbial population and immune response of broiler chicks fed aqueous extract of *Balanites aegyptiaca* and *Alchornea cordifolia* stem bark mixture. *United Journal for Research and Technology*, 2(2), 13-21.
19. Muritala, D.S., Alagbe, J.O., Ojebiyi, O.O., Ojediran, T.K., & Rafiu, T.A. (2022). Growth performance and haematological and serum biochemical parameters of broiler chickens given varied concentrations of *Polyalthia longifolia* leaf extract in place of conventional antibiotics. *Animal Science and Genetics*, 18(2), 57-71.
20. National Population Commission. (2006). *National Population Census*. Abuja, Nigeria: NPC.
21. National Research Council. (2012). *Nutrient Requirements of Poultry* (9th revised ed.). National Academy of Sciences.
22. Oke, U.K., Herbert, U., Ebuzoeme, C.O., & Nwachukwu, E.N. (2007). Effect of genotype on the haematology of Nigerian local chickens in a humid tropical environment. *Proceedings of the 32nd Annual Conference of Nigerian Society for Animal Production*.
23. Okoli, F.C., Okparaocha, C.O., Chinweze, C.E., & Udedibie, A.B.I. (2012). Physicochemical and hydrogen cyanide content of three processed cassava products used in feeding poultry in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 7(4), 334-340.
24. Olabanji, R.O., Farinu, G.O., Akinlade, J.A., & Ojebiyi, O.O. (2007). Growth performance and haematological characteristics of weaner rabbits fed cyanide in processed cassava peel meals on haematological and biochemical indices of growing rabbits. *Proceedings of the 35th Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society for Animal Production*, 212.
25. Oladunjoye, I.O., Ojebiyi, O.O., & Odunsi, A.A. (2008). Performance characteristics and egg quality of laying chicken fed lye-treated cassava peel meal. *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of ASAN*, 355-357.
26. Oladunjoye, I.O., Ojebiyi, O.O., & Amao, O.A. (2010). Effect of feeding processed cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) peel meal-based diet on the performance characteristics, egg quality and blood profile of laying chicken. *Agricultura Tropica et Subtropica*, 43(2).
27. Oladunjoye, I.O., Ojedapo, L.O., & Ojebiyi, O.O. (2005). *Essentials of Non-Ruminant Animal Production*. Positive Press.
28. Olafadehan, O.A., Olafadehan, O.O., Adewumi, M.K., Omotugba, S.K., & Daniel, N.E. (2008). *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual Conference, Nigeria Society of Animal Production*, 132-135.
29. Oleforuh-Okoleh, V.U., Adeolu, A.I., & Egbuhelu, C.O. (2010). Growth performance and economic benefits of cockerels fed diet containing graded levels of cassava peel meal. *Proceedings of the 35th Annual Conference of the Nigeria Society for Animal Production*, 324-326.
30. Odunsi, A.A., Ojifade, A.A., & Babatunde, G.M. (1999). Response of

broiler chicks to virginiamycin and dietary protein concentration in the humid tropics. *Archivos de Zootecnia*, 48(183), 317-325.

31. Togun, V.A., Oseni, B.S.A., Ogundipe, J.A., Arewa, T.R., Hameed, A.A., Ajonijeju, D.C., Oyeniran, A., Nwosisi, I., & Mustapha, F. (2007). Effects of chronic lead administration on the haematological parameters of rabbit – a preliminary study. *Proceedings of the 41st Conference of the Agricultural Society of Nigeria*, 341.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.